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Review Article

Insecticidal Effect of Castor Plant Leaf Powder (*Ricinus Communis*) on Cowpea Bruchid (*Callosobruchus Maculatus*) in Stored Cowpea Seeds

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ABSTRACT

Cowpea weevils (*Callosobruchus maculatus*) is a significant storage insect pest of cowpeas; it lays its eggs on the pods or seeds both in the field and in storage. The larva perforates the seeds and completes its life cycle there. It can cause loss if not controlled in time. This research aimed to assess the efficacy and effect of Castor plant leaf powder CLP (*Ricinus communis*) on cowpea weevils (*C. maculatus*) as an alternative for preserving cowpea seed at storage in Kebbi State, Nigeria. The study was carried out at Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology, Aliero; the study's experimental design was Completely Randomized Design with three replications. Data collected included the Number of dead weevils (NDW), seed weight Loss (SWL) and Number of Damaged Seeds (NDS) experiments. Significant difference of ($P < 0.05$) was recorded on the efficacy of (CLP), mortality assessment revealed Standard Insecticide (SI) as the highest (NDW) with 6.70 while in (CLP) variables with 10grams 5.40 was recorded followed by (CLP) 5.0gram with 4.37, (CLP) 2.5gram 3.80 were revealed, while the least value was revealed from Control (CON) with 2.53 and LSD0.005 value of 2.53 was also recorded. During Seed weight loss (SWL) analysis (CON) was the highest at 5.00, then (CLP) 2.5gram, 2.83 (SWL) was revealed, (CLP) 5.0gram 2.10, (CLP) 10gram 1.70 and (SI) with 1.33 (SWL) rate. However, the LSD0.005 was 0.73. Furthermore, the laboratory study of the effect of test insect on seed term as (NDS) was reported as such, (CON) variable with the high rate 26.67 (NDS), followed by (CLP) 2.5gram with 15.33, (CLP) 5.0gram, 12.00, then (CLP) 10gram with the rate of 9.33 while the lowest was (SI) 4.67 and with LSD0.005 number of 4.09 respectively. (CLP) have shown a great Bio-insecticidal activity against (*C. maculatus*) in storage.

Keywords: Castor Plant, Insecticidal effects, Cowpea Seeds, Cowpea weevils and Storage

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INTRODUCTION

In the tropical and subtropical areas of the world where it is grown, cowpeas (*Vigna unguiculata*) are among the most adaptable food legumes (Esang *et al.*, 2022). Nearly half a billion people process and eat the seeds as a cheap source of excellent vegetable protein, particularly in Africa, where the green revolution has had minimal effect (Hongbété *et al.*, 2017). It is also the most significant protein-rich legume in West Africa, making up between 60 and 80 per cent of the region's population's protein intake (Hongbété *et al.*, 2017). In addition to protein, it is pretty nutrient-dense, including 1.3% to 1.5% fat and 56% to 66% carbohydrates (Carlos, 2004; Esang *et al.*, 2022). The use of cowpea seed grain food effectively addresses the lack of protein in African people's diets, which are primarily composed of carbohydrates, cereals, roots, and plantains (Tony *et al.*, 2014). Different kinds of cowpeas are prepared for serving by cooking, canning, or freezing them in developed nations like the US and Australia (Esang *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, it has enormous potential and is essential to the socioeconomic development of Nigeria and West Africa in general and to the elimination of poverty, income generation, and nutritional and food security (Salihi *et al.*, 2018). In Africa, food grains are stored for brief durations of three to six months by farmers, food traders, and housewives (Ogendo *et al.*, 2004). The magnitude of crop production, market demands, and farmer needs all play a significant role in determining storage times. Small-scale farmers produce about 80% of these grains, which are then stored on the farm (Ajayi *et al.*, 2022). Grain storage guarantees food security, maximises profits, and provides seeds for upcoming planting seasons. However, maintaining seed viability and vigour, especially in tropical regions with high humidity, makes proper seed storage a major agricultural challenge (Salihi *et al.*, 2018). Insects and vertebrate pests are the main obstacles to grain storage in Nigeria and other third-world nations. The warm, humid climate of the tropics

exacerbates the physical and physiological changes in the stored produce (Ajayi *et al.*, 2022).

It has also been noted that the spread of infestation in traditional cowpea varieties in various parts of Africa was very slow during the dry seasons, with measurable losses only developing at the beginning of the rainy season. Over 20,000 field and storage pests harm an estimated one-third of agricultural products worth billions of dollars annually worldwide (Srivastava *et al.*, 2018). Grain post-harvest losses in sub-Saharan Africa are projected to be around \$4 billion annually (FAO, 2011). According to estimates from the Food and Agricultural Organization, between 1.5 and 2 million tons of Nigeria's yearly production of food grains are lost due to inadequate storage or pest infestation (Ajayi *et al.*, 2022). More than 200 insect pests on farms are known to infest stored grains (de Sousa *et al.*, 2020). Cowpea bruchids, are significant insect pests that threaten cowpea seeds (*Vigna unguiculata* Walp). Up to 80% of cowpea and maize infestations during storage are caused by this insect (Jood *et al.*, 2019).

Nigeria loses more than 6 million tons of grain annually due to damage sustained during food crop storage, which amounts to a staggering loss of almost five billion naira (Amadi *et al.*, 2023). Adopting pest management techniques has always been necessary because of the significant losses that take place in storage systems. Chemicals, which can be natural or synthetic items like oils, powders, and plant extracts, as well as non-chemical techniques including mechanical, physical, biological, and cultural strategies, are used to protect grains from insects in Nigeria and other African nations (Amadi *et al.*, 2023).

The widespread use of synthetic chemical insecticides, including carbamates, pyrethroids, and organophosphates, is supported by the claim that they work quickly and effectively to stop or lessen insect damage (Aulicky *et al.*, 2021). However, it has been shown that an ongoing dependence on pesticide

technology has drawbacks, including the potential for pest resurgence, secondary pest outbreaks, resistance development, and environmental risks like toxicity to non-target organisms and human poisoning (Stejskal *et al.*, 2021). It is thought that several characteristics of botanical insecticides give them a more significant edge over traditional pesticides. These include non-phytotoxicity, selectivity for target pests, reduced environmental persistence, and low mammalian toxicity, though this is not always true (Isman, 2006). Therefore, it is important to create safe substitutes for harmful synthetic pesticides as soon as possible. To find out if the Castor plant (*Ricinus communis*) at Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology Aliero (AFUSTA), North-West Nigeria, has insecticidal properties and is effective at preventing cowpea bruchids, or *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius), from attacking the plant while it is being stored, a survey will be carried out.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

In the laboratory of the Department of Crop Science, Faculty of Agricultural Science, Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology Aliero, the study was carried out in the Aliero local government of Kebbi State. The Aliero local government area, which had a total land area of 412 square kilometres and a population of about 125,783 people, was located at latitude 12° 16' 42" N and longitude 4° 27' 6" E concerning the equator (NPC, 2006). It shares borders with Birnin Kebbi LGA in the north, Jega LGA in the south, and Tambuwal LGA in Sokoto State in the east. Their primary occupations are business and agriculture, and their largest ethnic group is Hausa (Kalgo *et al.*, 2022). The region's climate is characterised by three distinct seasons: the hot, dry season, which begins in March and lasts until May or June; the hot, wet season, which lasts from May to June and September to October; and the cold, dry season, which lasts from November to February. The

seasonal average temperature is approximately 30°C, and the annual rainfall is approximately 500 mm. (Aliero *et al.*, 2013).

Collection and Identification of Test Plant Material (*Ricinus communis*)

The appropriate fresh Castor plant leaf was acquired from Birnin Kebbi, using the method used by Osariyekemwen *et al.* (2017), briefly as follows: In order to identify the plant, the test plant leaf was taken from Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, cut with a sterile shape knife while wearing sterile gloves, and then put straight into a sterile polythene bag. It was then taken straight to the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Sciences, Abdullahi Fodiyo University of Science and Technology Aliero, Nigeria. They were then returned to the undergraduate Crop Science laboratory for additional examination. Then, they were brought back to the Crop Science undergraduate laboratory for further analysis (Osariyekemwen *et al.*, 2017).

Preparation of Plant Leaf Powder

Following the collection and identification of the test plant leaf (Castor Plant: *Ricinus communis*), the leaf was cleaned under running water and allowed to dry in the shade for approximately seven (7) days before being sterilised and oven-dried for 24 hours at 60°C. Using an electric blender, the dried plant was ground into a fine powder, which was then standardised by passing it through a 0.1 mm mesh sieve. They were subsequently stored for later use in a water-proofed,

Handling Disinfestation of Cowpea (*V. unguiculata*) Seeds

White cowpea seeds that were recently supplied and insect-free were acquired from the Aliero market in Kebbi State, Nigeria. After removing any broken seeds

and debris from the grains, disinfestations were conducted in an oven set at 50°C for six hours to eradicate any potential insect life stages present in the grains. Before undergoing additional analysis, the grains were placed in plastic containers with tight lids and allowed to settle to room temperature for a full day. (Osariyekemwen *et al.*, 2017; Esang *et al.*, 2022).

Procurement and Culturing of Bean Weevil (*C. maculatus*)

At the Aliero market in Kebbi State, Nigeria, infected beans yielded the mature bean weevil *C. maculatus*. The harvested adults of *C. maculatus* were taken to the lab and stored in a jar with 100g of freshly cleaned and disinfected white cowpea seeds (*V. unguiculata*). After forty hours, the insects were removed, and the contaminated seeds were nurtured until fresh adult insects appeared. They were then gathered by sieve. After 24 hours, the container's sieved contents were once more sieved to extract the newly emerged adults between 0 and 3 days old. These adults were then employed in the experiments. (Salihu *et al.*, 2023).

Experimental Design

Briefly, the experiment was conducted using a complete randomised design: To allow for unrestricted aeration, 100g (i.e., 100g in triplicate, per Kilner jar) of cowpea seeds (*V. unguiculata*) were measured and put in Kilner Jar containers. The containers were then covered with lids. Following the introduction of ten (10) healthy and active cowpea weevils, the remaining three treatments were treated with different concentrations of Castor Leave Powder, ranging from low (2g), moderate (5g), and high (10g). The first and second treatments were used as controls and the recommended synthetic insecticide (Rambo Powder). Following the introduction of the plant treatments, the mixture was well combined and covered with muslin fabric. Every treatment was duplicated three times, and data

collection and recording were done every two days. (Salihu *et al.*, 2023).

Data Collection

Number of Dead Weevils

The number of dead weevils was determined and documented by using an office pin to probe the insect and then counting the dead weevils after two days. (Esang *et al.*, 2022).

Number of Seed Damage

The number of grains with holes and those that had been ground into powder were counted as weevil-caused damage at the conclusion of the storage period. The percentage of grain damage relative to the quantity of seeds (Esang *et al.*, 2022; Salihu *et al.*, 2023).

Seed Weight Loss

Before the experiment started, the initial weight of the cowpea seeds was determined, and the weight was also determined in the laboratory following the experiment. (Osariyekemwen *et al.*, 2017).

DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the least significant difference (LSD) test (LSD) were employed to separate the means of the data produced by this experiment at a significance level of 5%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Observation

In all treatments, all of the adult *C. maculatus* insects walked erratically, straying from the treated seeds and heading toward the top of the muslin cloth. In contrast, the insects in the control group moved within the gaps to reach the grains.

Mortality of *C. maculatus* adults during exposure to grains treated with castor leaf powder CLP term as Number of dead weevils

Table 1.0 displayed the results following exposure to CLP. Nevertheless, the chemically produced insecticide had the highest NDW mortality rate (6.7a), followed by the test plant Castor leaf powder (CLP) at 10.0-gramme concentration (5.40a NDW), CLP at 5.0 grammes with a 4.37ab mortality rate, and CLP 2.5 grammes with a 3.80bc rate. The control had the lowest NDW mortality rate (2.53c), as demonstrated. Additionally, an LSD0.005 value of 2.35 was noted throughout the evaluations.

Table 1.0: Mortality of *C. maculatus* adults during exposure to grains treated with castor leaf powder CLP term as Number of dead weevils

Variety	Number of Dead Weevils
SI	6.70a
CLP10	5.40a
CLP5.0	4.37abc
CLP2.5	3.80bc
CON	2.53c
LSD _{0.005}	2.35

Means with the same Letter(s) are not significantly different at 0.05 level of significant difference.

Effect of Cowpea Weevils *C. maculatus* on the Seeds term as Seed Weight Loss (SWL)

With a seed weight loss of 5.00 grams, the CON had the highest seed weight loss, followed by the Bioplant control term as variable CLP at 2.5 grams of concentration and a SWL rate of 2.83b. At 5.0 grams of concentration, the CLP showed a 2.10 bc rate, followed by CLP 10 grams with a 1.70 bd rate. However, as Table 2.0 below demonstrates, the least SWL rate was recorded using SI variables with 1.33d. The LSD0.005 value of 0.73 was further examined.

Table 2.0: Effect of Cowpea Weevils *C. maculatus* on the Seeds term as Seed Weight Loss (SWL)

Variety	Seed Weight Loss
SI	1.33d
CLP10	1.70cd
CLP5.0	2.10bc
CLP2.5	2.83b
CON	5.00a
LSD _{0.005}	0.73

Means with the same Letter(s) are not significantly different at 0.05 level of significant difference.

Assessments of damage caused by Cowpea Weevils *C. maculatus* on Cowpea Seeds term as Number of Damaged Seeds (NDS)

Table 3.0 below details the results of a laboratory analysis of the impact of *C. maculatus* on cowpea seed open treatment using CLP bioinsecticide and chemically manufactured insecticide as standard. With a rate of 26.67a, the variable CON had the highest NDS rate, followed by the Castor Plant Leaf concentration degree of CLP 2.5gram, which had an NDS of 15.33b; CLP with a concentration of 5.0gram, which had an NSD rate of 12.00bc; and variable CLP 10.0gram, which had an NDS rate of 9.33c. The lowest NDS was recorded from SI with a rate of 4.67d, and the LSD0.005 value was revealed as 4.09, respectively.

Table 3.0: Assessments of Damaged caused of Cowpea Weevils *C. maculatus* on Cowpea Seeds term as Number of Damaged Seeds (NDS)

Variety	Number of Dead Weevils
SI	4.67d
CLP10	9.33c
CLP5.0	12.00b
CLP2.5	15.33b
CON	26.67a
LSD 0.05	2.35

Means with the same Letter(s) are not significantly different at 0.05 level of significant difference.

DISCUSSIONS

Compared to synthetic pesticides, plant-based insecticides have shown to be attractive and effective substitutes for managing pests. They also present fewer risks to human health and/or the environment, making them potentially appropriate for use in integrated pest management programs (Yarou *et al.*, 2017). However, depending on the concentration level, the biological activities of castor leaf powder had varying efficacies. Our studies' findings indicate that castor leaf powder has the potential to be used as a substitute for chemically manufactured insecticides in the management of *C. maculatus* cowpea weevils. The castor leaf powder at 10 grams and SI were highly effective in our current trials. However, the test plant concentration at CLP 2.5 grams revealed 3.80 several dead weevils (NDW), whereas CLP 0 grams caused a significant mortality of roughly 5.40 a through exposure. Our findings showed that the death rate of the test organism decreased with decreasing concentrations and increased with increasing concentrations of the test plant. This study supports the findings of Tounou *et al.* (2011), who found that 20% concentrations of castor plant components cause roughly 67% of *C. maculatus* caterpillars to die. Furthermore, castor plant materials are known to cause larval death since they have been found to contain toxins, primarily ricin and ricinine (Frederiksson *et al.*, 2005) (Manoj *et al.*, 2017). On top

of that, a 100% death rate in *C. maculatus* was also observed by Ramos-López *et al.* (2010). As a result, Table 2's results demonstrate how well Castor leaf powder works to prevent cowpea weevils from reducing seed weight. Castor leaf powder CLP of 10gram concentration had a 1.70cd SWL rate, CLP 5gram 2.10bc, and CLP 2.5gram 2.83b. The control sample CON had the highest number of seed weight loss with a 5.00ad rate compared to the SI lease number of SWL 1.33d. According to the results, the weight loss of the seeds decreases when the concentration of the test plant increases, and vice versa. This result is comparable to that of Baukar *et al.* (2018), who found that after treating castor plants, the cowpea seed variation Sampea II had heavier seeds. Similarly, there was a significant ($P>0.05$) difference in the weight of the seeds before and after the experiment with the heavier cowpea seeds. This suggests that the plant extract did not affect the cowpea seeds' viability. Ilesanmi and Gungula (2013) confirm the above conclusion, stating that most edible plant extracts do not affect the viability of the seeds. It is possible to have viable seeds after treatment with plant extracts, as Manda *et al.* (2020) reported.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, products made from natural plants, like powdered castor leaves, have insecticidal properties and can be utilised to control cowpea weevils since it is more ecologically friendly and can be used instead of synthetic pesticides, which harm both the environment and creatures that are not their intended target. The ovicidal effect of castor leaf powder inhibits the emergence of mature *C. maculatus*.

RECOMMENDATION

In order to control cowpea weevils, this research study suggests using powdered castor leaves, which are far simpler and less expensive than synthetic chemicals, protecting the ecosystem overall.

Additionally, it is advised that farmers try to use botanicals for pest control or plant protection because of their economic feasibility, ease of use, technical simplicity, and environmental friendliness. The study's findings demonstrated that castor leaf powder can be used as a seed protectant. The test plant has also demonstrated its potential to be used more often for post-harvest cowpea seed protection in small-scale storage. Implementing this botanical control is advised in order to lessen environmental contamination. The plants could be applied straight to seeds that are intended to be preserved for later use because they are not known to be harmful to human health.

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